

**NECESSITY OF IMPROVEMENT OF RADIATION PROTECTION IN ANGIOGRAPHIC
LABORATORIES**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Angiographic examinations require long-term X-ray exposure during the procedure. Therefore, the rules of X-ray protection must be followed to protect patients and medical staff.

Materials and Methods: Four hospitals with 5 angiography systems were inspected for their workflow, and measurements were taken with a Dose Area Product meter (DAP meter) and a Kerma Air Product meter (KAP meter) to measure the radiation dose inside the laboratories. The results have been compared with international standards of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).

Results: The findings from Mongolia exceed the international standards for DAP (Dose Area Product) and KAP (Kerma Area Product) measurements. Specifically, the KAP values recorded were 2.46 and 0.56, while the standard for cardiac examinations is 0.25. For liver examinations, the measurements were 1.42 and 0.28, with a standard of 0.90. In cerebellum evaluations, KAP values of 0.54 and 0.29 were noted, compared to a standard of 0.40. Additionally, DAP measurements showed variations ranging from 70% to 1800% of the international standards for both heart and liver examinations.

Conclusion: It became clear that equipment older than 10 years is a big problem, as spare parts were not manufactured, and measurement software was not installed properly. Other issues include not having optional units for evaluating and fixing image quality; quality control performance is made by the Nuclear Energy Agency of Mongolia just once a year; not accepting image processing, delivering, and printing systems.

Key words: Radiation dosage, radiation protection, Dose Area Product, Kerma Air Product

INTRODUCTION

Angiography is a modern technology that utilizes special X-rays controlled by a dedicated screen to provide diagnostic and therapeutic measures for treating systemic diseases and disorders in the human body. This imaging system generates X-rays over an extended period to capture movements and changes from various angles¹. However, this results in increased radiation exposure for everyone in the room, including doctors, nurses, and patient². Therefore, it is essential to implement proper protection for all individuals present to ensure that the health benefits of the procedure outweigh the potential risks associated with radiation exposure. Radiation protection encompasses a broad range of practices, including the use of surface materials, shielding devices, and protective clothing as direct measures. Additionally, it involves standards, procedures, and training as indirect measures. Regular assessments of these protective measures are necessary to determine whether they are sufficient for ensuring safety.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four hospitals in Ulaanbaatar, the capital and biggest city of Mongolia, were compared with international standards in terms of requirements for radiation protection of Angiography systems. The hospitals are:

- UB SongDo Hospital (private hospital)
- National Cancer Center (NCC, national hospital)
- 1st general hospital (national hospital)
- 3rd general hospital (national hospital)

The third general hospital has 2 angiography systems, the other hospitals have one each.

In order to compare the five angiography systems and their environment with the international standards, information about them must be collected. The information should be as follows:

- Dimensions of the control and the device room
- The number of patients to estimate the workload

- Technical specifications of the Angiography machine and filters
- Radiation dose measurement

Measurements of the radiation doses are performed with measurement devices for radiation dose³. The Dose Area Product (DAP) is measured with a special device named the DAP meter (Figure 1). It is used to determine the amount of radiation absorbed by the skin of the patient. The Kerma Air Product (KAP) has another measurement device (Figure 2). It is for the determination of radiation dose, which is spreading in the air and therefore harmful for nurses and doctors inside the angiography room⁴. Both modern devices replaced the old generation ionization chambers (Figure 3) that are sometimes still in use in Mongolia. The ionization chambers measure the X-ray, beta, and gamma radiation and record it in kilovolts (kV), milliamperes (mA), and minutes (min.)

Figure 1: Flat panel ion chamber (DAP meter)

Figure 2: Flat panel ion chamber (KAP meter)

Figure 3: Ionization chamber

Ethical considerations require a regular check of safety measures and X-ray protection, especially in cases of longer X-ray exposure. Therefore, the Mongolian National University of Medical Sciences and the Ministry of Health have a keen interest in this kind of research. An approval for the research was not required as the measuring devices did not interfere with the standard procedures during the duties in the laboratories.

RESULTS

Table 1.

Working space in Angiography in Mongolian hospitals

Hospital name	UB SongDo Hospital (Multistar Plus)	NCC- (Polydiagnost C2)	1 st Hospital- (Allura CV20)	3 rd Hospital- (Integris H-5000)	3 rd Hospital- (Allura X per FD 20 Biplane)	International standard
Control room (M ²)	39	10	13	21	21	8
Device	42	32	56	42	84	48

room (M²)

Table 1 shows the available sizes of five angiography locations in four different hospitals in Ulaanbaatar in comparison with international standards. All inspected control rooms have 125-488% of the international standard size. The device rooms have 67-175% of the international standard size.

Figure 4. Comparison of the number of patients in five different angiography locations

Figure 4 shows the number of patients that are diagnosed in the hospitals (per day, per month, per year). The rate of angiograms is highest at the 3rd Hospital Allura, covering about 36% of all patients per year.

- Technical specifications of angiography

Table 2.

Age, energetically, and filtering specifications of the five angiography locations

No	Hospital name	Manufacturer	Model	Production year	Installation year	X-ray tube voltage (kV)	X-ray tube current (mA)	Filter (mmAl)
1	UB SongDo	SIEMENS (Germany)	Multistar Plus	1999	2009	150	1000	1.5+1.0
2	NCC	PHILIPS (Australia)	Polydiagnost C2	1996	2005	125	1000	2.5
3	3rd Hospital	PHILIPS (Australia)	Integris H-5000	1999	2007	125	1000	2.5
4	3rd Hospital	PHILIPS (USA)	AlluraX per FD 20/20	2012	2013	125	1000	3.5

5	1st Hospital	PHILIPS (Netherlands)	Allura CV20	2012	2013	125	1000	2.5
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Table 2 shows that three of five angiography devices in the inspected locations are older than 17 years, even though they had been installed in Mongolia not later than 12 years ago. Current and voltage are in similar in old and new devices. After the UB SongDo device got a second filter, the filter size in all cases is 2.5 mm or higher.

- Radiation dose of devices measured with KAP and DAP meters

Table 3.

KAP* and DAP† for different scans in different hospitals compared with international standards

№	Hospital	Heart scan		Liver scan		Neurological scan	
		KAP (gray)	DAP (gray/cm ²)	KAP (gray)	DAP (gray/cm ²)	KAP (gray)	DAP (gray/cm ²)
1	1 st Hospital (Allura CV20)	2.46	150.13	1.42	311.84	0.54	101.40
2	3 rd Hospital (Integris H-5000)	-	25.02	-	18.98	-	-
3	3 rd Hospital (Allura X per FD 20 Biplane),	0.56	71.82	0.28	74.93	0.29	84.40
4	International standard	0.25	36.00	0.90	17.00	0.40	19.00

Table 3 shows that the radiation dose in the tested hospitals is higher than described in international standards. Measurements could not be obtained in all scans from all angiography locations‡.

DISCUSSION

Our research shows that the radiation dose in Angiography that the doctors, nurses, and patients receive is much higher than it should be according to the international standards⁵. This kind of research has never been done in Mongolia before. It will be necessary to increase the number of locations inspected and to collect more data from the scans

* *Dose Area Product (DAP)*- Measurement of the radiation dose per area for the patient (gray/cm²)

† *Kerma Air Product (KAP)*- Measurement of radiation dose in the air (gray)

‡ Locations without any DAP and KAP data were removed from the table.

performed at these locations. Further research should include the doctor's experience and knowledge about radiation protection and the device, and whether it is possible to reduce the radiation dose with the training of the workers or not.

In Mongolia, the diagnosis and services with Angiography have reached international levels like developed countries. However, safety is a big difficulty because of the old angiography machines that were donated. The costs for these machines are getting higher because spare parts for maintenance and repair are becoming increasingly difficult to obtain the older the machine gets.

In four national and two private hospitals, there are seven Angiography systems, 60% of which are already old, and their image quality is poor. The 1st and the 3rd hospitals have new modern technology Angiography systems (manufactured in 2012), which is very good because they can offer services with similar possibilities as in developed countries. Due to the high number of patients and the frequent use of the device, serious problems have already occurred with these devices, e.g., melting and burning of the X-ray tube and damage to the operating system. All these issues lead to high maintenance costs.

Doctors and nurses do not fully understand radiation protection and the difficulties and dangers of the equipment. Therefore, they cannot comply with international standards. Old protection devices, a lack of protection measures, personnel, and a high workload for each worker cause additional troubles.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results show that the dimensions of the rooms are, in general, fitting with international standards, however, rooms where the systems are installed are sometimes not big enough to use the system effectively. The number of angiography patients is high at the 3rd general hospital because it specializes in the diagnosis of heart and blood vessel problems, heart failure, and stroke. All of these illnesses have become more common in recent times.

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